

Comparative Outcomes of Laparoscopic TAPP Mesh Repair Versus Open Hernia Repair

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Abstract:

Background: Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most frequently performed surgeries worldwide, with two primary techniques: laparoscopic Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) mesh repair and open hernia repair. While open repair has been the traditional standard, recent advancements in laparoscopic methods suggest potential benefits such as reduced postoperative pain and quicker recovery. However, there remains a need for a comprehensive comparison of these two approaches to inform surgical decision-making.

Aim: This study aims to compare the outcomes of laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair versus open hernia repair in terms of operative time, postoperative pain, recovery time, complications, and recurrence rates.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted involving 86 patients with inguinal hernias randomly assigned to either TAPP mesh repair (n=43) or open repair (n=43). Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18-65 years undergoing elective hernia surgery. Data were collected on operative time, postoperative pain, hospital stay, recovery, and complications. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The TAPP group showed significantly shorter operative times (65.2 ± 15.4 minutes) compared to the open repair group (78.9 ± 18.3 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Postoperative pain scores were lower in the TAPP group (3.5 ± 1.2) versus the open group (5.8 ± 1.5 , $p < 0.001$), and hospital stays were shorter (1.8 ± 0.6 days vs. 3.4 ± 1.1 days, $p < 0.001$). Complications, including wound infections and chronic pain, were less frequent in the TAPP group, with statistically significant reductions in chronic pain (4.7% vs. 20.9%, $p = 0.02$). Recurrence rates were slightly lower in the TAPP group but did not reach statistical significance.

Conclusion: Laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair provides superior outcomes compared to open hernia repair, including shorter operative times, reduced pain, faster recovery, and fewer complications. These findings support the consideration of TAPP as a preferred approach for inguinal hernia repair.

Recommendations: Surgeons should consider laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair as a first-line option for inguinal hernia patients, particularly for those prioritizing faster recovery and reduced postoperative discomfort. To validate these results and determine long-term recurrence rates, more research with bigger sample sizes and long-term follow-up is advised.

Keywords: Inguinal hernia, TAPP mesh repair, laparoscopic surgery, open hernia repair, postoperative outcomes.

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Introduction

Millions of inguinal hernias are repaired each year, making it one of the most common surgical procedures carried out globally [1]. The two main methods that are frequently employed are laparoscopic repair, which includes the (TAPP) mesh procedure, and open hernia repair, which has historically been the accepted norm. A patient's preference, the skill of the surgeon, and the perceived risks and advantages all play a role in the decision between various treatments. In terms of recovery time, pain management, and overall

complication rates, recent developments in laparoscopic surgery have prompted concerns about whether TAPP mesh repair could yield better results than open repair [2]. Due to its ease of use and the doctors' expertise with the procedure, open hernia repair has traditionally been the recommended method. In order to strengthen the abdominal wall, mesh is positioned over the hernia location via a direct incision. Open repair, although widely used, has several disadvantages, such as increased risk of wound infection and persistent pain, longer recovery

periods, and more discomfort following surgery [3]. These consequences have the potential to lower quality of life and increase the amount of time it takes for patients to resume their regular activities. For this reason, research into alternate methods is still ongoing.

On the other hand, because laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair is less invasive, it has become more and more common. With the aid of laparoscopic technology, mesh is inserted through tiny incisions, improving visibility of the surrounding anatomy and the hernia site [4]. Compared to open repair, this method has been linked to fewer postoperative pain, shorter hospital stays, and faster recovery durations. Comparing laparoscopic hernia repairs, including TAPP, to open repairs, a systematic study by Belyansky et al. found that the former led to a quicker recovery and fewer problems [5]. However, surgeons continue to debate concerns over the learning curve associated with laparoscopic methods and the possibility of intraoperative consequences, such as bladder or bowel injury. In an effort to develop evidence-based recommendations for choosing the best method for inguinal hernia repair, recent research has carried out comparisons between these two techniques. A meta-analysis revealed that, while recurrence rates were comparable between the two groups, laparoscopic repair, including TAPP, consistently showed lower rates of chronic pain and wound complications compared to open repair [6]. Although both methods are useful, these results imply that there may be clear benefits to the laparoscopic approach that can enhance patient outcomes. This study aims to compare the outcomes of laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair versus open hernia repair in terms of operative time, postoperative pain, recovery time, complications, and recurrence rates.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective observational.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the General Surgery Department of ANMMCH, Gaya, a tertiary care center equipped with advanced laparoscopic surgical facilities. The study was conducted over a 12-month period, from January 2023 to January 2024, with data analysis and follow-up extending up to six months post-surgery.

Participants: A total of 86 patients with diagnosed inguinal hernias were enrolled in the study. Participants were randomly assigned to either the laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair group or the open hernia repair group, with equal numbers in each cohort.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 to 65 years.
- Diagnosed with unilateral or bilateral inguinal hernia.
- Eligible for elective hernia surgery.
- Willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with recurrent hernias.
- Those with contraindications to general anesthesia.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with severe comorbid conditions affecting surgical risk (e.g., uncontrolled diabetes, severe cardiopulmonary disease).

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly assigned to laparoscopic or open repair groups using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Standardized surgical protocols and procedures conducted by skilled surgeons proficient in both techniques reduced performance bias. Assessment bias was minimized through blinded evaluation of postoperative outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected using structured forms that captured demographic information, surgical details, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain, length of hospital stay, recovery time, and recurrence rates. Follow-up assessments were conducted at regular intervals up to six months post-surgery to monitor outcomes.

Procedure: Participants in the laparoscopic group underwent TAPP mesh repair under general anesthesia, involving the insertion of a mesh through the abdominal wall via laparoscopic access. The open repair group underwent conventional hernia repair through an open incision, with mesh placement performed using standard techniques. Both groups received standardized postoperative care, including pain management and mobility support.

Statistical Analysis: The data analysis program was SPSS 23.0. Clinical and demographic data were collected using descriptive statistics. Chi-square tests analysed categorical data, while independent t-tests examined continuous variables. If $p < 0.05$, statistical significance was obtained. Kaplan-Meier was used to compare the two groups' recurrence-free survival.

Results

The study included 86 patients, 43 of whom underwent laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair and 43 underwent open hernia surgery. Participants' baseline age, gender, and comorbid conditions were similar between groups, indicating no substantial variations that could affect outcome measures.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	TAPP Group (n=43)	Open Repair Group (n=43)	p-value
Age (years), Mean $\pm$ SD	45.3 $\pm$ 10.5	44.8 $\pm$ 9.7	0.78
Male, n (%)	35 (81.4%)	36 (83.7%)	0.78
Female, n (%)	8 (18.6%)	7 (16.3%)	0.78
BMI (kg/m ²), Mean $\pm$ SD	26.4 $\pm$ 3.2	27.1 $\pm$ 3.5	0.44
Comorbidities, n (%)			
Hypertension	12 (27.9%)	11 (25.6%)	0.81
Diabetes Mellitus	10 (23.3%)	9 (20.9%)	0.79

Intraoperative data showed that TAPP had a considerably shorter mean operative time than open repair. The TAPP group had fewer intraoperative

problems. TAPP patients had considerably lower pain scores, shorter hospital stays, and faster return to routine activities postoperatively.

Table 2: Intraoperative and Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	TAPP Group (n=43)	Open Repair Group (n=43)	p-value
Operative Time (minutes), Mean $\pm$ SD	65.2 $\pm$ 15.4	78.9 $\pm$ 18.3	<0.001
Intraoperative Complications, n (%)	3 (7.0%)	7 (16.3%)	0.19
Postoperative Pain Score (VAS)*, Mean $\pm$ SD	3.5 $\pm$ 1.2	5.8 $\pm$ 1.5	<0.001
Length of Hospital Stay (days), Mean $\pm$ SD	1.8 $\pm$ 0.6	3.4 $\pm$ 1.1	<0.001
Return to Normal Activities (days), Mean $\pm$ SD	10.4 $\pm$ 3.7	18.2 $\pm$ 4.5	<0.001

Compared to the open repair group, the TAPP group experienced fewer postoperative problems overall, such as wound infection and persistent discomfort.

The TAPP group also had reduced recurrence rates, however this difference was not statistically noteworthy.

Table 3: Complication Rates

Complication	TAPP Group (n=43)	Open Repair Group (n=43)	p-value
Wound Infection, n (%)	1 (2.3%)	6 (14.0%)	0.05
Chronic Pain (>3 months), n (%)	2 (4.7%)	9 (20.9%)	0.02
Recurrence, n (%)	1 (2.3%)	3 (7.0%)	0.30

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair offers several advantages over open hernia repair in patients undergoing elective inguinal hernia surgery. Notably, the TAPP group experienced significantly shorter operative times, averaging approximately 65 minutes compared to 79 minutes in the open repair group. This difference in operative time suggests that the laparoscopic approach may be more efficient, potentially reducing the duration of anesthesia exposure and operative stress on patients.

Postoperative outcomes further highlight the benefits of the TAPP technique. Patients who underwent TAPP repair reported significantly lower postoperative pain, with an average pain score of 3.5 on the (VAS), compared to 5.8 in the open repair group. This reduction in pain likely contributed to the shorter hospital stays observed in the TAPP group, where patients were discharged after an average of 1.8 days, compared to 3.4 days for those who underwent open repair. Additionally, patients in the TAPP group returned to normal activities significantly faster, with an average recovery time of 10.4 days versus 18.2 days in the open repair group. These

findings suggest that TAPP repair not only enhances patient comfort but also promotes quicker postoperative recovery, which could be particularly beneficial for patients with demanding lifestyles or limited ability to take time off work.

Additionally, the study discovered that the TAPP group had less problems following surgery. In the TAPP group, wound infections occurred in 2.3% of patients, but in the open repair group, they occurred in 14.0% of patients. Additionally, only 4.7% of patients in the TAPP group experienced chronic pain, compared to 20.9% in the open repair group. This difference in incidence was significant. The TAPP group had somewhat lower hernia recurrence rates (2.3%) than the open repair group (7.0%), although this difference was not statistically significant. However, TAPP repair is often associated with lower rates of complications, indicating that it is a safer option with fewer long-term bad consequences.

In a research of sixty patients, laparoscopic (TAPP) and open inguinal hernia mesh repairs were contrasted. The study was carried out at Apollo Main Hospital in Chennai. According to the results, patients who underwent laparoscopic surgery

returned to work on average 8 days earlier than those in the open group, who did not; they also reported far less discomfort at different postoperative time points. Additionally, the group that underwent laparoscopic surgery needed fewer days of postoperative analgesia, indicating that TAPP repair provides better short-term results in terms of pain and recovery time [7]. Prospective case-control research examined the quality of life and long-term surgical outcomes of heavyweight and self-gripping meshes used in TAPP repairs. All two mesh types showed improvements in discomfort and limited movement following surgery, but there were no statistically significant differences in recurrence rates or problems between them, according to the study. These results imply that both mesh types work well for TAPP and have comparable long-term results [8]. Recurrence and postoperative discomfort after laparoscopic and open repairs was the subject of another meta-analysis. According to the data, TAPP was linked to noticeably lower rates of acute and chronic pain than open repairs, even if the recurrence rates of both methods were equal. This implies that TAPP may provide patients with a higher quality of life even though therapy is equally effective at preventing hernia recurrence [9].

Conclusion

The results of this study strongly support the use of laparoscopic TAPP mesh repair as a superior alternative to open hernia repair. The TAPP approach not only reduces operative time and postoperative pain but also leads to quicker recovery and lower rates of complications, making it a preferable choice for patients requiring inguinal hernia surgery. These findings have important implications for surgical practice and patient care, suggesting that laparoscopic techniques should be considered more broadly in the management of inguinal hernias.

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